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ФАН ВА ТАЪЛИМ

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ИЛИМ ҲӘМ ТӘЛИМ

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**FAUNA AND ECOLOGY OF VARIOUS AGRO-CENOZOIC PHYTONEMATODES
DISTRIBUTED IN THE REGIONS OF THE REPUBLIC OF KARAKALPAKISTAN**

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***Summary:** This article will study the fauna and ecology of phytonematodes, which are harmful to various crops grown in agriculture in the Republic of Karakolpagestan, considered an important region of Uzbekistan. In particular, according to the State Statistics Committee, in 2023 alone, more than 317,400 tons of grain crops, more than 35,000 tons of legumes, 94,700 tons of tomatoes, 53,200 tons of cucumbers, 96,000 tons of potatoes, and more than 183,500 tons of melons for food products were grown in the Republic of Karakolpagistan. The Republic of Karakalpakstan is characterized by its unique climate and soil conditions, and various crops are grown, however, despite the fact that the region is increasingly threatened by phytonematodes in agriculture. These microscopic worms damage plant roots, cause a number of symptoms ranging from slow growth to wilting of the plant's body, and consequently significantly lose yield. Therefore, scientific research on the relationship of phytonematodes to plants is important, as they provides detailed information about the fauna and individual species of phytonematodes. The main purpose of the study is to study and analyze the fauna and ecology of various agro-cainozoic phytonematodes distributed on the territory of the Republic of Karakalpakstan. Analysis of the distribution characteristics of phytonematodes in the root of the plant and the soil around it is determined to determine the types and distribution patterns of nematodes.*

***Key words:** phytonematodes, fauna; agrocnosis; agriculture; parasite; soil; individ; type.*

Introduction: In contemporary agriculture, various adverse changes in cultivated plants are arising due to multiple stress factors. Among these, nematodes (Nematoda) represent a class of parasitic organisms that cause significant damage to agricultural crops [25]. Nematodes comprise a diverse group of free-living and parasitic species adapted to various habitats. These nematodes possess adaptations that enable them to thrive in different environments and can be found in both plants and animals [40]. Phytoparasitic nematodes are widespread across various plant and crop species worldwide, leading to substantial economic losses. Currently, there are over 4,100 species of phytoparasitic nematodes globally, resulting in annual economic losses in agriculture estimated to be around \$125 billion. In recent years, the demand for agricultural and natural products has been increasing globally, highlighting the significant impact of nematodes [30]. Most nematode species are associated with plants, making scientific research on the relationships between phytoparasitic nematodes and plants crucial. In addition to pressing global food security issues, concerns about pest and disease control are intensifying. This is related to the forecasted risks of climate change and the emergence of new pests, including nematodes. Such research provides comprehensive information about the fauna and specific species of phytoparasitic nematodes. Our study aims to investigate and analyze the fauna and ecology of various agrocnosis phytoparasitic nematodes in the territory of the Republic of Karakalpakstan. According to several studies, the quantitative and qualitative composition of phytoparasitic nematodes is not constant and varies over time and across different environments. These changes can be attributed to various factors such as crop cultivation practices, plant nematode specificity, plant growth and development, and environmental changes.

LITERATURE REVIEW.

Structure, Classification, and Types of Nematodes: Nematodes are a type of animal typically characterized by their microscopic size, cylindrical body shape, and lack of an external skeleton. These organisms can be found living freely in terrestrial and aquatic environments, as well as parasitizing the organs of plants and animals. There are over 25,000 described species of nematodes [17, 44]. Some literature sources indicate that there are more than 25,000 species, with approximately 10,000 free-living marine and terrestrial nematodes, 3,500 invertebrate parasites, and

12,000 vertebrate parasitic nematodes [21, 31]. Nematodes are among the most diverse and abundant groups of invertebrates on Earth, notable for their sensitivity to pollutants and ecological disturbances [16, 19, 28]. They are highly adaptable to nearly all types of ecosystems and are considered one of the most species-rich groups of microorganisms [10]. Nematodes are some of the most important and numerous animals in the animal kingdom, capable of surviving in almost any environment [1, 29]. Commonly referred to as "roundworms," these organisms have a fundamentally simple structure yet are ubiquitous, appearing in nearly all types of multicellular living organisms. When considering all animal species on Earth, nematodes may have more diverse types than any other animal group [6, 34, 36]. The body structure of nematodes closely resembles that of worms (see Figure 1).

Figure 1. Nematode structure (www.geeksforgEEKS.org).

The development of nematodes comprises five stages, including four larval stages (L1, L2, L3, L4) and one adult stage (L5) [9]. The nematode's body is a slender cylinder, tapering at both ends. The muscles of nematodes are divided into four groups, with dorsal and ventral muscle groups on the right and left sides extending longitudinally along its body. These dorsal and ventral muscle groups are innervated separately and contract alternately to produce dorso-ventral flexion. This up and down movement, where the animal bends first to one side and then to the other, is characteristic of nematodes. Nematodes cannot twist or rotate because they only have longitudinal muscles, and thus cannot move by alternating the contraction and expansion of different body parts. They can only move dorsally or ventrally [4, 24, 25, 39, 44]. Nematodes have four nerves running along the length of their bodies: the dorsal nerve, the ventral nerve, and two lateral nerves located at the midpoints of each side. If a nematode worm is cut longitudinally and viewed under a microscope, it can be observed that the nerves are positioned in quadrants. The lateral nerves are mainly sensory, while the dorsal and ventral nerves transmit impulses that cause muscle contractions. Therefore, lateral nerves transmit impulses to the brain, whereas the dorsal and ventral nerves transmit impulses from the brain to the muscles. The brain, called the cerebral ganglion, is located ventrally in the anterior nerve ring and controls the nematode's neural tissue [8, 13, 40, 45]. The digestive system of nematodes is simple, consisting of a straightforward intestine. The nematode's mouth often has jaws, and in parasitic forms, they can actively bite through tissue. Free-living forms use their jaws to capture prey or to grasp ingested debris. The remainder of the intestine is a simple tube, only one cell layer thick, with folds or loops that connect it to the body wall [4, 12, 15, 32, 44].

Plant-Parasitic Nematodes in Soil: In a global context where the demand for natural agricultural products is steadily increasing, particularly in rapidly growing populations like Uzbekistan, the cultivation of high-quality and nutritious agricultural products is a pressing issue. Combating plant diseases and pests is a primary challenge in agriculture, as achieving high yields and sustainable cultivation requires the prudent use and management of ecosystems [35]. Among various adverse stress factors in agricultural production, nematodes are particularly significant. Despite their microscopic size, nematodes cause the loss of billions of dollars worth of crops

annually, and virtually all crops worldwide are affected by at least one type of nematode parasite [5]. Nematodes are the most important and widespread soil invertebrates, occupying a crucial position in all trophic levels of the soil ecosystem [11, 45]. Plant-parasitic nematodes are a major stress factor in crop production [43]. These nematodes are referred to as plant parasites because they directly assimilate nutrients from plants. Phytonematodes possess a needle-like structure called a stylet, which aids in piercing plant cell walls and extracting nutrient-rich sap [3]. Accurate identification of nematode species is essential for selecting appropriate control methods. The economic impact of yield losses due to nematodes is varied, often associated with decreased crop quality and productivity. Taxonomy based on nematode morphology is complex due to species variability, but tools and techniques based on biochemical and molecular markers can successfully diagnose a wide range of nematode species [7, 27]. Nematodes can damage nearly all parts of plants, including roots, stems, leaves, fruits, and seeds, either individually or in conjunction with other soil microorganisms [41]. Although the recognition of nematodes as a significant cause of plant diseases on a global scale has only been acknowledged since the mid-20th century, nematodes have been studied for over 150 years. The most harmful plant-parasitic nematodes are root-knot nematodes (RKNs), and *Meloidogyne* sp [2]. Worldwide, chemical pesticides are used to combat these parasites in vegetable crops [38]. However, this approach also eliminates beneficial soil organisms, highlighting the need for alternative methods to neutralize parasitic nematodes. Sustainable production systems should employ eco-friendly alternatives to maintain and enhance the health of antagonistic organisms. Soils with high antagonistic potential do not foster pathogens [14, 18, 42].

METHODS.

Research area natural climate: The natural conditions of the Republic of Karakalpakstan are somewhat unfavorable, which is directly related to its geographical location. The region is situated between 40°C and 45°C latitudes, which ensures a specific moderation of the climate, a key factor of natural conditions. However, due to its considerable distance from oceans and seas, and its location between the Karakum and Kyzylkum deserts, the region exhibits distinctly continental climatic features. These features are characterized by scorching and dry summers, and harsh and dry winters (Figure 2).

Figure 2. The average annual amount of climate change in the Republic of Karakalpakstan (<https://map.worldweatheronline.com/>).

In the Republic of Karakalpakstan, average temperature changes between 2010 and 2023 are illustrated in figure 4. Temperature ranges from -12 to 42 °C are possible. The sharp rise in temperature is attributed to the decrease in soil moisture and unique hydrothermal regimes. Significant variations were observed during the rainy season. The highest temperature peak was recorded in 2019.

Annual average precipitation in Karakalpakstan between 2010 and 2023 showed significant variability, ranging from 100 mm to 220 mm. Rainfall amounts varied from season to season, with some years experiencing sufficient rainfall from strong storms, while others recorded abundant precipitation. In 2019, the highest rainfall was recorded, positively impacting soil fertility and agricultural productivity. Competent storms lower air temperatures, increase soil moisture content, and in some years freeze and replant crop fields.

Figure 3. Average annual precipitation of the Republic of Karakalpakstan (<https://map.worldweatheronline.com/>).

Decrease in precipitation and higher temperatures during summer months lead to increased evaporation from the soil. Evaporation amounts to 1280-1470 mm, with atmospheric precipitations contributing 320-363 mm, resulting in a moisture deficit of 960-1107 mm. The wind direction varies, with significant differences observed in January and July. The prevailing wind direction predominantly affects the northern, central, and eastern regions towards the southwest, while in the southern-western regions, the wind predominantly blows from the north. The prevailing wind blows from the northern direction, partly shifting towards the northeast.

Object of Study: Scientific research was conducted in the districts of Turtkul, Beruni, Amudaryya, Khojayli, and Chimbay in the Karakalpakstan Republic. Samples were collected from these areas (Figure 4).

1- point Turtkul

41°53'25.7"N 61°22'52.0"E

2- point Beruni

41°54'57.9"N 60°49'42.6"E

3- point Amudaryya

42°10'08.3"N 60°13'06.3"E

4- point Khojayli

42°23'21.6"N 59°17'24.7"E

5- point Chimbay

42°56'22.4"N 59°38'23.3"E

Figure 4. The coordinates of the point from which the soil samples are obtained are, 2024-y.

Soil samples are believed to have been taken from sites previously planted with family crops Cucurbitaceae. Soil and root samples were taken from the upper 30 cm soil layer.

Sample Collection va Laboratory Analysis: Samples were systematically collected from various locations within the specified districts to ensure a comprehensive representation of the area's environmental conditions. The sampling sites were chosen based on their ecological significance and potential impact on the study's objectives. Nematodes were extracted using the modified Baermann method and the route methods as specified by Whitehead and Hemming [20, 26, 33, 37, 46]. The species composition of nematodes was determined according to the generally accepted method. The identification of nematode species composition was carried out using a BX53 microscope with a light source, "OLYMPUS", SC-180 (Japan, 2018). In calculating the dominance

level of phytonematodes present in plant roots and rhizosphere soils, the individual percentages of all identified species were calculated (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Detection of nematodes in soil sample in the laboratory, 2024-y.

According to the classification, species that make up more than 10.0% of the total number of individuals in the detected species are called eudominants, 5.1-10.0% are dominants, 2.1-5.0% are subdominants, 1.1-2.0% are residents, and less than 1.0% are subprecedents [22, 23]. To identify nematodes isolated from samples, temporary and permanent microscopic preparations were prepared according to the methods of E.S. Kiryanova and E.L. Krall [47].

By adhering to these methodological frameworks, the study aims to provide a robust and detailed understanding of the environmental conditions in the Karakalpakstan Republic.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION.

Ecological groups of identified phytonematodes: As a result of the studies, research was carried out in four regions of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, Beruniy, Amudaryo, Khojayli, Chimbay districts into 6 large ecological groups according to the relationship of phytonematodes with plants and the method of nutrition identified in the soil of certain Palak crops and their root environment (Figure 6).

Figure 6. Ecological groups of phytonematodes according to their feeding method

According to the above method of nutrition, 6 large ecological groups are not uniformly distributed in the research areas. The faunistic complex of Cucurbitaceae family plants and their root environment nematodes in soils was dominated by devisaprobionts feeding on plant residues. Studies of the phytonematodes of boring and melon plants from Cucurbitaceae family crops and the soils of their root environment have identified 2 classes (*Adenophorea*, *Secernentea*) of the younger Class, 4 categories (*Dorylaimida*, *Rhabditida*, *Aphelenchida*, *Tylenchida*) of the order, 12 families, 22 generations from 39 species. Of the phytonematode species identified, *Rhabditida species* are in the leading position (19 generations), accounting for 48.7% of the total identified species. Next are *Aphelenchida* (11; 28.2%) and *Tylenchida* (8; 20.5%). *Representatives* of the *Dorylaimida* (1; 2.5%) category were found in the lowest number.

During the studies, the species composition and distribution of phytonematodes identified in Cucurbitaceae family crops and their ecological relationship with plants were analyzed in a biotope cross-section. The 39 species that make up the nematode fauna of Cucurbitaceae family crops are mainly A in the classification and description of ecological groups according to their nutritional and vital characteristics. A. Paramonov, G.W. The work of Yeates and others was used [48,49,50,51]. A.A. Based on the system proposed by Paramonov, plant nematodes are classified into *pararisobionts*, *eusaprobionts*, *devisaprobionts*, *mycogelmints*, and *parasitic* phytoelmints. These ecological groups are also in turn separated into several more subgroups [48]. *Pararisobionts* usually live freely in the soil around the root. Most species feed on plant cell sap but do not cause serious damage to the plant. In our material, *pararisobionts* contain 1 species in a small number of groups.

Conclusion: In the districts of the Republic of Karakalpakstan Turtkul, Beruni, Amudarya, Khojayli, and Chimbay, a group of *devisaprobionts* of nematodes prevails on the soils of Cucurbitaceae family crops and their root circumference. A study on phytonematodes of *Cucumis sativus* L and *Cucumis melo* plants and their root circumference soils revealed 2 younger classes, 4 category, 12 families, 22 generation, and 39 species. Among these, *Rhabditida's* representatives took the leading position, accounting for 48.7% of the total. Next were *Aphelenchida* and *Tylenchida*, respectively 28.2% and 20.5%. Representatives of the Dorylaimida series, on the other hand, suffered in the fewest numbers. These results provide important information about the ecological environment and phytonematode distribution. Comparison of the composition and population density of nematode species in the areas under study of Cucurbitaceae family crops and their root circumference soils showed a significant difference in the composition of the nematode fauna and its structure under different conditions. Apparently, this difference is explained by the condition of the soil, the peculiarity of the plant, and the dependence on agrotechnical measures applied to crops.

References:

1. Aleuy OA, Kutz S (2020) Adaptations, life-history traits and ecological mechanisms of parasites to survive extremes and environmental unpredictability in the face of climate change. *International Journal for Parasitology: Parasites and Wildlife* 12:308–317. doi: 10.1016/j.ijppaw.2020.07.006
2. Almohithef AH, Al-Yahya FA, Al-Hazmi AS, Dawabah AAM, Lafi HA (2020) Prevalence of plant-parasitic nematodes associated with certain greenhouse vegetable crops in Riyadh region, Saudi Arabia. *Journal of the Saudi Society of Agricultural Sciences* 19:22–25. doi: 10.1016/j.jssas.2018.05.001
3. Bernard GC, Egnin M, Bonsi C (2017) The Impact of Plant-Parasitic Nematodes on Agriculture and Methods of Control. In: Shah MM, Mahamood M (eds) *Nematology - Concepts, Diagnosis and Control*. InTech
4. Bird AF, Bird J (1991) *The structure of nematodes*, 2. ed. Academic Pr, San Diego
5. Bozbuga R, Lilley CJ, Knox JP, Urwin PE (2018) Host-specific signatures of the cell wall changes induced by the plant parasitic nematode, *Meloidogyne incognita*. *Sci Rep* 8:17302. doi: 10.1038/s41598-018-35529-7
6. Bridge J, Starr J (2007) *Plant Nematodes of Agricultural Importance: A Colour Handbook*, 0 ed. CRC Press
7. Carneiro RMDG, Lima FSDO, Correia VR (2017) Methods and Tools Currently Used for the Identification of Plant Parasitic Nematodes. In: Shah MM, Mahamood M (eds) *Nematology - Concepts, Diagnosis and Control*. InTech
8. Carta LK, Handoo ZA, Hoberg EP, Erbe EF, Wergin WP (2009) Evaluation of Some Vulval Appendages in Nematode Taxonomy. *Comparative Parasitology* 76:191–209. doi: 10.1654/4302.1
9. Chabaud AG (1955) Essai d'interprétation phylétique des cycles évolutifs chez les Nématodes parasites de vertèbres. Conclusions taxonomiques. *Ann Parasitol Hum Comp* 30:83–126. doi: 10.1051/parasite/1955301083
10. Cunha BP, Fonseca G, Amaral ACZ (2022) Diversity and Distribution of Cyatholaimidae (Chromadorida: Nematoda): A Taxonomic and Systematic Review of the World Records. *Front Mar Sci* 9:836670. doi: 10.3389/fmars.2022.836670
11. De Ley P, Blaxter M (2002) Systematic Position and Phylogeny. In: Lee D (ed) *The Biology of Nematodes*. CRC Press, pp 1–30

12. Decraemer W, Coomans A, Baldwin J (2013) 1. Morphology of Nematoda. In: Schmidt-Rhaesa A (ed) Nematoda. DE GRUYTER, pp 1–60
13. Dorris M, De Ley P, Blaxter ML (1999) Molecular Analysis of Nematode Diversity and the Evolution of Parasitism. *Parasitology Today* 15:188–193. doi: 10.1016/S0169-4758(99)01439-8
14. Dutta TK, Khan MR, Phani V (2019) Plant-parasitic nematode management via biofumigation using brassica and non-brassica plants: Current status and future prospects. *Current Plant Biology* 17:17–32. doi: 10.1016/j.cpb.2019.02.001
15. Félix M-A, De Ley P, Sommer RJ, Frisse L, Nadler SA, Thomas WK, Vanfleteren J, Sternberg PW (2000) Evolution of Vulva Development in the Cephalobina (Nematoda). *Developmental Biology* 221:68–86. doi: 10.1006/dbio.2000.9665
16. Folix M-A (1999) Evolution of developmental mechanisms in nematodes. *J Exp Zool* 285:3–18. doi: 10.1002/(SICI)1097-010X(19990415)285:1<3::AID-JEZ2>3.0.CO;2-J
17. Geisen S, Briones MJ, Gan H, Behan-Pelletier VM, Friman V-P, De Groot GA, Hannula SE, Lindo Z, Philippot L, Tiunov AV, Wall DH (2019) A methodological framework to embrace soil biodiversity. *Soil Biology and Biochemistry* 136:107536. doi: 10.1016/j.soilbio.2019.107536
18. Giannakou IO, Panopoulou S (2019) The use of fluensulfone for the control of root-knot nematodes in greenhouse cultivated crops: Efficacy and phytotoxicity effects. *Cogent Food & Agriculture* 5:1643819. doi: 10.1080/23311932.2019.1643819
19. Griffiths BS, Römbke J, Schmelz RM, Scheffczyk A, Faber JH, Bloem J, Pérès G, Cluzeau D, Chabbi A, Suhadolc M, Sousa JP, Martins Da Silva P, Carvalho F, Mendes S, Morais P, Francisco R, Pereira C, Bonkowski M, Geisen S, Bardgett RD, De Vries FT, Bolger T, Dirilgen T, Schmidt O, Winding A, Hendriksen NB, Johansen A, Philippot L, Plassart P, Bru D, Thomson B, Griffiths RI, Bailey MJ, Keith A, Rutgers M, Mulder C, Hannula SE, Creamer R, Stone D (2016) Selecting cost effective and policy-relevant biological indicators for European monitoring of soil biodiversity and ecosystem function. *Ecological Indicators* 69:213–223. doi: 10.1016/j.ecolind.2016.04.023
20. Hernández-Chavarría F, Avendaño L (2001) A simple modification of the Baermann method for diagnosis of strongyloidiasis. *Mem Inst Oswaldo Cruz* 96:805–807. doi: 10.1590/S0074-02762001000600011
21. Hugot J-P, Baujard P, Morand S (2001) Biodiversity in helminths and nematodes as a field of study: an overview. *Nematol* 3:199–208. doi: 10.1163/156854101750413270
22. Ilieva KM (2015) Nicienie glebowe Parku Skaryszewskiego w Warszawie – zagęszczenie i różnorodność zespołów w dwóch siedliskach. *Studia Ecologiae et Bioethicae* 119-133 c
23. Kasprzak K, Niedbała W (1981) Wskaźniki biocenotyczne stosowane przy porządkowaniu i analizie danych w badaniach ilościowych. In: Górny M, Grum L (eds) *Metody stosowane w zoologii gleby*. Warszawa
24. Katz M, Despommier DD, Gwadz RW (1989) The Nematodes. In: *Parasitic Diseases*. Springer US, New York, NY, pp 1–64
25. Kiontke K, Fitch DHA (2013) Nematodes. *Current Biology* 23:R862–R864. doi: 10.1016/j.cub.2013.08.009
26. Kiryanova ES, Krall EL (1969) Parasitic nematodes of plants and measures to combat them. Nauka, Russia, Leningrad
27. Kumar V, Khan MR, Walia RK (2020) Crop Loss Estimations due to Plant-Parasitic Nematodes in Major Crops in India. *Natl Acad Sci Lett* 43:409–412. doi: 10.1007/s40009-020-00895-2
28. Malan AP, Ferreira T (2017) Entomopathogenic Nematodes. In: Fourie H, Spaul VW, Jones RK, Daneel MS, De Waele D (eds) *Nematology in South Africa: A View from the 21st Century*. Springer International Publishing, Cham, pp 459–480
29. McSorley R (2003) ADAPTATIONS OF NEMATODES TO ENVIRONMENTAL EXTREMES. *Florida Entomologist* 86:138–142. doi: 10.1653/0015-4040(2003)086[0138:AONTEE]2.0.CO;2
30. Mesa-Valle CM, Garrido-Cardenas JA, Cebrian-Carmona J, Talavera M, Manzano-Agugliaro F (2020) Global Research on Plant Nematodes. *Agronomy* 10:1148. doi: 10.3390/agronomy10081148
31. Morand S, Bouamer S, Hugot J-P (2006) Nematodes. In: Morand S, Krasnov BR, Poulin R (eds) *Micromammals and Macroparasites*. Springer Japan, Tokyo, pp 63–79
32. Mulder C, Schouten AJ, Hund-Rinke K, Breure AM (2005) The use of nematodes in ecological soil classification and assessment concepts. *Ecotoxicology and Environmental Safety* 62:278–289. doi: 10.1016/j.ecoenv.2005.03.028
33. Narzikulova M.F., Eshova H. S. (2023) POTATO PHYTONEMATODES OF SAMARKAND REGION. *iec* 2:209–214
34. Oostenbrink M, Loof PAA, Yassin AM (1970) Plant Parasitic Nematodes in the Sudan. *Nematol* 16:567–571. doi: 10.1163/187529270X00775

35. Pinto AG, Kos T, Puškarić J, Vrandečić K, Benković-Lačić T, Brmež M (2024) Soil Ecosystem Functioning through Interactions of Nematodes and Fungi Trichoderma sp. Sustainability 16:2885. doi: 10.3390/su16072885
36. Schmidt-Rhaesa A (2013) 5. Outline on nematode phylogeny. In: Schmidt-Rhaesa A (ed) Nematoda. DE GRUYTER, pp 171–172
37. Sigariova DD, Karpilyk VG (2015) Parasitic Nematodes in Flowering and Ornamental Plants: Effect of Parasites on the Plants and Response of the Plants to the Presence of Nematodes. Vestnik Zoologii 49:427–432. doi: 10.1515/vzoo-2015-0049
38. Sikandar A, Zhang M, Wang Y, Zhu X, Liu X, Fan H, Xuan Y, Chen L, Duan Y (2020) In vitro evaluation of *Penicillium chrysogenum* Sneh1216 against *Meloidogyne incognita* (root-knot nematode). Sci Rep 10:8342. doi: 10.1038/s41598-020-65262-z
39. Singh S, Singh B, Singh AP (2015) Nematodes: A Threat to Sustainability of Agriculture. Procedia Environmental Sciences 29:215–216. doi: 10.1016/j.proenv.2015.07.270
40. Thomas B, Murphy DJ, Murray BG (2017) Encyclopedia of applied plant sciences, Second edition. Academic Press is an imprint of Elsevier, Oxford
41. Tileubayeva Z, Avdeenko A, Avdeenko S, Stroiteleva N, Kondrashev S (2021) Plant-parasitic nematodes affecting vegetable crops in greenhouses. Saudi Journal of Biological Sciences 28:5428–5433. doi: 10.1016/j.sjbs.2021.05.075
42. Topalović O, Hussain M, Heuer H (2020) Plants and Associated Soil Microbiota Cooperatively Suppress Plant-Parasitic Nematodes. Front Microbiol 11:313. doi: 10.3389/fmicb.2020.00313
43. Treonis AM, Unangst SK, Kepler RM, Buyer JS, Cavigelli MA, Mirsky SB, Maul JE (2018) Characterization of soil nematode communities in three cropping systems through morphological and DNA metabarcoding approaches. Sci Rep 8:2004. doi: 10.1038/s41598-018-20366-5
44. Van Den Berg E, Marais M, Swart A (2017) Nematode Morphology and Classification. In: Fourie H, Spaull VW, Jones RK, Daneel MS, De Waele D (eds) Nematology in South Africa: A View from the 21st Century. Springer International Publishing, Cham, pp 33–71
45. Van Den Hoogen J, Geisen S, Routh D, Ferris H, Traunspurger W, Wardle DA, De Goede RGM, Adams BJ, Ahmad W, Andriuzzi WS, Bardgett RD, Bonkowski M, Campos-Herrera R, Cares JE, Caruso T, De Brito Caixeta L, Chen X, Costa SR, Creamer R, Mauro Da Cunha Castro J, Dam M, Djigal D, Escuer M, Griffiths BS, Gutiérrez C, Hohberg K, Kalinkina D, Kardol P, Kergunteuil A, Korthals G, Krashevskaya V, Kudrin AA, Li Q, Liang W, Magilton M, Marais M, Martín JAR, Matveeva E, Mayad EH, Mulder C, Mullin P, Neilson R, Nguyen TAD, Nielsen UN, Okada H, Rius JEP, Pan K, Peneva V, Pellissier L, Carlos Pereira Da Silva J, Pitteloud C, Powers TO, Powers K, Quist CW, Rasmann S, Moreno SS, Scheu S, Setälä H, Sushchuk A, Tiunov AV, Trap J, Van Der Putten W, Vestergård M, Villenave C, Waeyenberge L, Wall DH, Wilschut R, Wright DG, Yang J, Crowther TW (2019) Soil nematode abundance and functional group composition at a global scale. Nature 572:194–198. doi: 10.1038/s41586-019-1418-6
46. Whitehead AG, Hemming JR (1965) A comparison of some quantitative methods of extracting small vermiform nematodes from soil. Ann Applied Biology 55:25–38. doi: 10.1111/j.1744-7348.1965.tb07864.x
47. Кирьянова Е.С. ЕС, Кралль ЭЛ (1969) Паразитические нематоды растений и меры борьбы с ними. Ленинград, Москва
48. Парамонов А.А. Основы фитогельминтологии. – Москва: Наука, 1962. Т. 1. – 480 с.
49. Thorne G. Principles of Nematology. - Toronto, London, 1961. – 553 p.
50. Yeates G.W. Feeding types and feeding groups in plant and soil nematodes // Pedobiologia, 1971. V.2. № 2. – P. 173-179.
51. Yeates G.W., Bongers T., R.G.M. de Goede, D.W. Freckman and S.S. Georgieva. Feeding Habits in soil Nematode in Families and Genera-An Outline for Soil Ecologists. // Journal of Nematology, 25(3), 1993. – P. 315-331

Rezyume: *Ushbu maqolada O'zbekistonning muhim hududlaridan hisoblangan Qoraqolpog'iston Respublikasida qishloq xo'jaligida yetishtiriladigan turli ekinlarga zarar keltiradigan fitonematodalarining faunasi va ekologiyasi o'rganilgan. Xususan davlat statistika qo'mitasining ma'lumotlariga ko'ra, birgina 2023 yilda Qoraqolpog'iston Respublikasida 317 ming 400 tonnadan ortiq donli ekinlar, 35 ming tonnadan ortiq dukkakli don ekinlari, 94 ming 700 tonna pomidor, 53 ming 200 tonna bodring, 96 ming tonna kartoshka va 183 ming 500 tonnadan ortiq oziqbop poliz ekinlari yetishtirilgan. Qoraqolpog'iston Respublikasi o'ziga xos iqlimi va tuproq sharoiti bilan ajralib turadi, turli ekinlar yetishtiriladi. Biroq, shunday bo'lishiga qaramay mintaqa qishloq xo'jaligi fitonematodalar tomonidan tobora ko'proq xavf ostida qolmoqda. Ushbu mikroskopik qurtlar o'simlik ildizlarini zararlab, o'sishning susayishidan tortib, o'simlik tanasining so'lib qolishgacha bo'lgan bir qator alomatlarini keltirib chiqaradi va natijada hosilning sezilarli*

darajada yo'qolishiga olib keladi. Shuning uchun fitonematodalarning o'simliklar bilan aloqasi haqidagi ilmiy tadqiqotlar muhim ahamiyatga ega, chunki ular fitonematodalarning faunasi va alohida turlari haqida batafsil ma'lumot beradi. Tadqiqotning asosiy maqsadi Qoraqalpog'iston Respublikasi hududida tarqalgan turli agrotsenoz fitonematodlarining faunasi va ekologiyasini o'rganish va tahlil qilishdan iborat. O'simlik ildizi va atrofida tuproqda fitonematodalarning tarqalish xususiyatlarini tahlil qilish nematodalarning turlari va tarqalish qonuniyatlarini ochib berilishi aniqlanadi.

Резюме: В этой статье будет изучена фауна и экология фитонематод, которые наносят вред различным культурам, выращиваемым в сельском хозяйстве Республики Каракалпакстан, считающейся важным регионом Узбекистана. В частности, по данным Госкомстата, только в 2023 году в Республике Каракалпакстан было выращено более 317 400 тонн зерновых культур, более 35 000 тонн бобовых, 94 700 тонн томатов, 53 200 тонн огурцов, 96 000 тонн картофеля и более 183 500 тонн бахчевых культур для производства продуктов питания. Республика Каракалпакстан характеризуется своими уникальными климатическими и почвенными условиями, здесь выращиваются различные сельскохозяйственные культуры, однако, несмотря на то, что региону все чаще угрожают фитонематоды в сельском хозяйстве. Эти микроскопические черви повреждают корни растений, вызывают ряд симптомов, начиная от замедления роста и заканчивая увяданием растения и, как следствие, значительной потерей урожая. Поэтому научные исследования взаимосвязи фитонематод с растениями важны, поскольку они дают подробную информацию о фауне и отдельных видах фитонематод. Основной целью исследования является изучение и анализ фауны и экологии различных агрокайнозойских фитонематод, распространенных на территории Республики Каракалпакстан. Для определения типов и закономерностей распространения нематод проводится анализ характеристик распределения фитонематод в корне растения и почве вокруг него.

Kalit so'zlar: fitonematoda, fauna; agrotsenoz; qishloq xo'jaligi; parazit; tuproq; individ; tur.

Ключевые слова: фитонематоды, фауна; агроценоз; сельское хозяйство; паразит; почва; индивид; тип.